

**AN APPRAISAL OF THE NUTRITIONAL
VALUE AND UTILIZATION OF COCOYAM
AND WATER YAM IN ONDO TOWN**

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Abstract

The study appraised the nutritional value of some cocoyam and water yam dishes and also investigated the utilization of cocoyam and water yam among the people of Ondo town. One hundred and ten (110) home makers were selected for the study, using multi-stage and simple random sampling. Nutritional analysis was performed on samples of some cocoyam and water yam dishes (isikolo, ikokore, ojojo, eberipo, cocoyam ball and pottage) while relevant data were collected with the aid of a closed ended questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. The result of data analysis showed that 59% of the respondents consume cocoyam and water yam dishes, while 25% were not familiar with dishes produced from the tubers. 46% were of the opinion that the two yams were food for the poor, 20% said the yams had no

nutritional value while 50% claimed they were allergic to the two yams. Result of the nutritional analysis also revealed that the water yam dishes averagely contained 8.1g of protein, 297.9k cal of energy and 9.5g of fat (all in 100g portion). Cocoyam dishes contained 9.1g of protein, 375.5 kcal of energy and 17.0g of fat. It was therefore recommended that nutrition education programmes through the use of mass media and home visits by community health workers be employed. This should be targeted at enlightening the public on the nutritional value of cocoyam and water yam dishes.

Introduction

There are different types of root tubers namely, yam (which could either be white, yellow or water yam), sweet potato, cassava and cocoyam. These crops are largely produced in our locality and are depended on for survival in many parts of Nigeria. Most of our energy supply is derived from these crops. Most of the tubers are seasonal foods; white yam is cheaper and more available during the rainy season, water yam and cocoyam are readily available and cheaper towards the end of the rainy season. Anthonio and Isaun (1994) reports that cocoyam and water yam are planted during the raining season but are not abundant in the local market nowadays, due to unfavourable weather conditions, lack of interest displayed by farmers, poor yield in terms of tuber quality and quantity. Poor yields have been reported from the crops probably due to poor method of cultivation, lack of fertilizer application or poor method of fertilizer application. All these factors contribute to the scarcity of water yam tubers. The largest proportion of yam produced annually is marketed as the fresh tubers, only some very small fraction goes to the market in processed forms.

Food is a prime necessity of life and the importance of good nutrition in the growth and development of human beings cannot be overemphasized. To be healthy and strong, our bodies need a balanced diet of different nutritious food everyday. Among all the root vegetables or crops that are nutritionally rich in carbohydrate are cocoyam and water yam. According to Anthonio and Isaun (1994), water yam and cocoyam, are part of the most important sources of vitamins and mineral salts, provided they are adequately and correctly prepared and cooked so as to retain their nutrients. Anyakoha (2000) reported that cocoyam and water yam can be made nutritious and served in many ways through the use of different ingredients and methods of preparation (could be fried, roasted or boiled) thereby making these dishes worthwhile contribution to the nutritional value of our body requirements.

Cocoyam has several species but the common ones are Xanthosoma sagittifolium (tannia), which originated from the West Indies and Colocasia esculentum (taro), which was introduced from India. Both types grow to about 180 centimetres in height and have very large leaves. The young leaves are sometimes eaten but the main source of food is the underground stem of corn. In many areas of Nigeria, cocoyam is considered to be inferior to other yams. This may be due to the small size of the tuber. Nutritionally, cocoyam is similar to the other yams and could provide valuable variation to the diet. It could be eaten boiled, made into yam balls, porridge, pounded yam etc. According to Anthonio and Isaun (1994), cocoyam contains a good quantity of carbohydrate, some vitamins, minerals and incomplete

protein. Both the root and leaves of the cocoyam must be cooked well, if not, the oxalates present therein could be irritating to the throat. The *taro* type of cocoyam is boiled and eaten as yam; it could also be made into powdery flour; which can be used as wheat substitute for better mixture. The *tannia* type is usually used as thickening agent in soups and it could also be served as boiled vegetable which has to be thoroughly cooked in order to reduce the acidic substance (oxalic acid). According to Bello (1992), cocoyam contains an acidic substance, which has an irritating effect on the throat but the cooking of cocoyam by traditional methods removes the unpleasant property. Anthonio and Isaum (1994) also reported that cocoyam contains a fairly good source of calcium and the young leaves are also rich in mineral salts and vitamins. Although, the leaves are richer in nutrient, they are not as commonly used as the tubers and the quantity used do not make significant nutrient contribution.

Water yam (*Dioscorea alata*) is in the same family as the other yams but is used in different ways. However, water yam in many parts of Nigeria is considered an inferior food to white and yellow yam. Water yam is high in water content and vary in colour from white to brown and red. In some West African countries like Nigeria, especially the South-West, yam varieties are classified locally according to shape and quality of tubers. Some yam varieties are unfortunately less mealy and palatable when boiled. Nutritionally, water yam has significantly more protein (about 7.7%), minerals (5.2%) and more digestible carbohydrate than other species of yam. The peels are digestible and contain high concentration of proteins. According to Bello (1992), water yam has a

less gluey texture than the other varieties when cooked and can be readily mashed or creamed into a digestible yam dish, which is suitable for infant feeding. Water yam is generally grated and fried to accompany a main meal or used as a snack known as *ojojo* in Yorubaland. The use of water yam as yam flour is not very widespread in the South-West of Nigeria and therefore it should be more popularized, as it is richer in food value than the more popular white yam which is also rich in carbohydrate with traces of protein, mineral salts and vitamins.

Water yam and cocoyam are good for preparing variety of dishes but many home makers do not have the basic knowledge of how to use cocoyam and water yam to provide valuable variation to the family diet. Some do not even believe that cocoyam and water yam have nutritional values like white and yellow yams, while many also regarded them as food for the poor.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to evaluate the nutritional content of some cocoyam and water yam dishes and find out the level of utilization of cocoyam and water yam among the home makers in Ondo town.

Specifically, the study

- i. inquire about the consumption of cocoyam and water yam in Ondo, town.
- ii. found out the beliefs and reaction of home makers in Ondo about cocoyam and water yam consumption,
- iii. found out the responses of home makers in Ondo on the possibility of cocoyam and water yam providing valuable variation to the diet.

- iv. analysed the protein, energy and fat value of some cocoyam and water yam dishes and their percentage contribution to Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA)

Methodology

Design of the Study

This research work was an experimental study on the nutritional value of some cocoyam and water yam products and also a descriptive survey through the use of questionnaire on the utilization of cocoyam and water yam among home makers in Ondo town.

Population

The population for the study comprised all home makers in Ondo town and all possible dishes prepared from cocoyam and water yam.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

Six different dishes (*ikokore, ojojo, isikolo, cocoyam pottage, ebiripo, and cocoyam balls*) commonly prepared from cocoyam and water yam were purposively selected for the study. In addition, one hundred and ten (110) home makers were randomly selected for the administration of questionnaire.

Instrumentation

Close ended questionnaire was used to obtain data on the utilization of cocoyam and water yam.

Method of Data Analysis

Samples were analyzed for protein, mineral, fat and energy contents by the method of AOAC (2009).

Analysis of Data and Discussion

Table 1: Responses on the consumption of cocoyam and wateryam of households in Ondo town

S/N	Items	Frequency of responses	Percentage (%)
1.	Which of these do you consume?		
	(a) Cocoyam and water yam	65	59
	(b) Cocoyam only	13	12
	(c) Water yam only	19	17
	(d) None	13	12
	Total	110	100
2.	Are you familiar with the different dishes produced from cocoyam and water yam?		
	(a) Yes	80	73
	(b) No	30	27
	Total	110	100
3.	Which of these meals do you enjoy taking?		
	(a) <i>Ikokore</i>	29	26
	(b) Cocoyam ball	5	5
	(c) Water yam ball	33	30
	(d) Cocoyam pottage	25	23
	(e) <i>Isikolo</i>	1	1
	(f) <i>Amuyale</i> (cocoyam pudding)	8	7
	(g) None	9	8
	Total	110	100
4.	How many times in a week do you take meals from cocoyam and water yam?		
	(a) Once	68	62
	(b) Twice	22	20
	(c) Thrice	8	7
	(d) Everyday	4	4
	(e) None	8	7
	Total	110	100

From Table 1 above, it is shown that 59% of the respondents eat both cocoyam and water yam, 12% of the respondents eat cocoyam only, while 17% of the respondents eat water yam only. Also from the table, 73% of the respondents claimed to be familiar with the different dishes produced from cocoyam and water yam, 27% of the respondents are not familiar with the dishes. The table also showed that 62% of the respondents eat cocoyam and water yam once in a week, while 20% eat them twice in a week and 45 eat them every day.

Table 2: Responses of home makers on the belief and reactions to cocoyam and water yam consumption.

S/N	Items	Frequency of responses	Percentage (%)
5	What is your belief about cocoyam and water yam consumption		
	(a) Food of the poor	51	46
	(b) No nutritional value	22	20
	(c) Poisonous	10	9
	(d) Normal food like other food items	27	25
	Total	110	100
6.	Which of the food items are you allergic to?		
	(a) Cocoyam only	30	27
	(b) Water yam only	15	14
	(c) Both	10	9
	(d) None	55	50
	Total	110	100

Table 2 above presented responses on the belief and reactions of respondents to cocoyam and water yam consumption. The analysis showed that 40% of the

respondents believed that the food items were meant for the poor people, 20% thought the food items had no nutritional value, 9% believed the foods contain poisonous substances, while 25% regarded them as normal food items. Furthermore, 27% of respondents claimed to be allergic to cocoyam, 14% to water yam, 9% to both cocoyam and water yam, while 50% of the respondents had no allergy to the food items.

Table 3: Responses of home makers on the possibility of cocoyam and water yam providing valuable variation to the diet

	Items	Yes	%	No	%
7.	Do you think cocoy am and water yam can provide valuable variation to the diet?	96	87	14	13
8.	If enlightened, will you consume cocoyam and water yam dishes as much as white yam dishes?	70	64	40	36
9.	Do you wish to learn new ways of preparing cocoyam and water yam?	91	83	19	17
10.	If yes, will you include such meal in your menu?	80	80	22	20

From the result presented in Table 3, 87% of the respondents reacted positively, while 13% opposed the idea. In addition, 64% of respondents indicated their intention to consume cocoyam and water yam dishes as much as the dishes prepared from white yam, if enlightened. Also, 83% of respondents wished to learn new ways of preparing cocoyam and water yam, while 80% promised to include such new meals in their family menu.

Table 4: Protein Value of Water yam Dishes (g/100g)

S/N	Dishes	Protein (g)	RDA (g)	% RDA MET
1.	<i>Isikolo</i>	8.9	49	18.16%
2.	<i>Ikokore</i>	10.3	49	21.02%
3.	<i>Ojojo</i>	5.1	49	10.40%
	Total Protein Content	24.3		49.58
	Mean (x)	8.1		16.53

From table 4, *isikolo* contains 8.9g of protein. For an average male adult, the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) for protein is 49g per day. This indicates that *isikolo* can provide 18.16% of the RDA, *Ikokore* contains 10.3g of protein and can also provide 21.02% of the RDA. *Ojojo* contained 5.1g of protein, and will meet 10.40% of the RDA.

Table 5: Energy Value of Water yam Dishes (kcal)

S/N	Dishes	Energy (Kcal)	RDA (Kcal)	% RDA MET
1.	<i>Isikolo</i>	291.1	3,000	9.70
2.	<i>Ikokore</i>	364.6	3,000	12.15
3.	<i>Ojojo</i>	238.1	3,000	7.93
	Total Energy Value	893.8		29.78
	Mean (x)	297.9		9.93

Table 5 shows that *isikolo* contained 291.1 Kcal of energy in 100g portion and can therefore meet 9.7% of the RDA for energy of an average male adult. *Ikokore* contains 364.6 Kcal of energy to meet 12.15% of energy, while *ojojo* contained 238.1 Kcal of energy to meet 7.93% of energy of an average male adult.

Table 6: Fat Value of Water yam Dishes (g/100g)

S/N	Dishes	Fat (g)	RDA (g)	% RDA MET
1.	Isikolo	3.94	73.6	5.35
2.	Ikokore	9.27	73.6	12.59
3.	Ojojo	15.41	73.6	20.93
	Total Fat Value	28.62		38.89
	Mean (x)	9.54		12.96

Table 6 presented the fat value of water yam dishes. From the table, *isikolo* contained 3.94g of fat, therefore, meeting 5.35% of the RDA for fat of an average male adult. *Ikokore* contained 9.27g fat, while *ojojo* contains 15.41g of fat to meet 12.59% and 20.93% of RDA respectively.

Table 7: Protein Value of Cocoyam Dishes (g/100g)

S/N	Dishes	Protein (g)	RDA (g)	% RDA MET
1.	Cocoyam ball	6.2	49	12.65
2.	Cocoyam pottage	7.8	49	15.9
3.	<i>Eberipo</i>	13.2	49	26.93
	Total Protein Content	27.2		55.48
	Mean (x)	9.1		18.49

From the result of nutritional analysis presented in Table 7 for cocoyam dishes, cocoyam ball contains 6.2g of protein, meeting 12.65% of RDA of an average male adult. It also showed that cocoyam pottage contains 7.8g protein, while *eberipo* contains 13.2g to meet 15.9% and 26.93% RDA of protein requirement respectively.

Table 8: Energy Value of Cocoyam Dishes (Kcal)

S/N	Foods	Energy (Kcal)	RDA (Kcal)	% RDA MET
1.	Cocoyam ball	579.31	3,000	19.31
2.	Cocoyam pottage	325.3	3,000	10.84
3.	<i>Eberipo</i>	221.98	3,000	7.39
	Total Energy Value	1126.59		37.54
	Mean (x)	375.53		12.51

Table 8 presented the energy value of cocoyam products. From the table, cocoyam ball contained 579.31 Kcal which can meet 19.31% of RDA energy of an average male adult. Cocoyam pottage contains 325.3 Kcal, while *eberipo* contains 221.98Kcal to supply 10.84% and 7.39% of RDA energy, respectively.

Table 9: Fat Value of Cocoyam Dishes (g/ 100g)

S/N	Dishes	Fat (g)	RDA (g)	% RDA MET
1.	Cocoyam ball	39.53	73.6	53.70
2.	Cocoyam pottage	10.47	73.6	14.22
3.	<i>Eberipo</i>	1.02	73.6	1.38
		51.02		69.30
	Mean (x)	17.01		23.10

From the fat value of cocoyam dishes in Table 9, cocoyam ball contains 39.53g of fat which can supply 53.70% of RDA fat of an average male adult. It also showed that cocoyam pottage contained 10.47g of fat which can meet 14.22% RDA, while *eberipo* contains 1.02g of fat meeting only 1.38% of RDA fat of an average male adult.

Discussion

From the result of the study as presented in the tables, it was observed that about half (46%) of the respondents believed that cocoyam and water yam are foods meant for the poor people. Some (50%) claimed to be allergic to cocoyam and water yam, but during further interview about 64% wished to consume cocoyam and water yam, if adequately enlightened on the nutritional value of the tubers. Also, 83% of the respondents wished to learn new ways of preparing cocoyam and water yam apart from the old methods they were familiar with. However, the second part of this research work, which was based on the nutritional analysis of cocoyam and water yam products showed clearly that all the food samples i.e *isikolo*, *ikokore*, *ojojo*, cocoyam pottage and *eberipo* contains essential food nutrients e.g proteins, energy, fat and they complement other food items in providing the nutrients required by the body for proper body functioning.

Ojofeitimi and Olufokunbi (2000), in a previous study, notes that cocoyam contains 4.3 to 6.4% of digestible crude protein, 0.20 to 0.39% of fat, 376 to 383 calories in 100g; water yam contain, 5.1% digestible crude protein 0.32% fat and 373 calories in 100g. Tables 7, and 8 above show that cocoyam products prepared in this study contained 9.1g of protein in 100g portion, 17.01g of fat in 100g portion and 375.53Kcal of energy respectively. Tables 4,5 and 6 show that water yam products contain 8.1g of protein in 100g portion, 9.54g of fat in 100g portion and 297.93Kcal of energy respectively.

Conclusion

The results of this study show that over half of the respondents (59%) consume cocoyam and water yam. Most of them (73%) are familiar with the dishes produced from the two crops and take meals from them once a week (62%). Some of the respondents (46%), believe that cocoyam and water yam are food for the poor people. Very few respondents (27% and 14%) claimed to be allergic to meals produced from cocoyam and water yam respectively. Products prepared in this study can contribute significantly to Recommended Daily Allowances of protein, fat and energy.

Recommendations

From the data collected and duly analyzed, the following recommendations are made:-

Nutrition education programmes are necessary through the use of mass media, especially radio and television programmes to enlighten members of the public on the nutritional value of cocoyam and water yam dishes and the valuable variation they can provide to the diet.

Home visit is another important strategy. The Local Government Authorities should employ more community health workers to visit villages and communities and give health talks to different families. Through this process their nutritional problems would be identified and they could be taught how to make use of available local food items to correct their diet problems.

It is suggested that the correct type of yam for the respective yam dishes should be used; this is because cocoyam, for example, cannot be used for

ikokore, but it is very good for making *eberipo*. Dishes prepared from cocoyam and water yam can be enriched by accompanying them with proteinous foods like fish, shrimps, eggs and vegetables, which contain vitamins and mineral salt.

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